

A SURVEY OF SKILLS ACQUISITION IN HOME ECONOMICS AS A WAY FORWARD TO PROMOTE NIGERIAN ECONOMY. A CASE STUDY OF COLLEGES OF EDUCATION IN ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA

YADUMA MARTHA

Department of Home Economics, Adamawa State College of Education, Hong

Phone No: 08138744081

Email: marthayaduma@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14648325>

Abstract

The study surveyed skills acquisition in Home economics as a way forward to promote Nigerian economy. A case study of Colleges of Education in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The study specifically focuses on various areas of Home Economics offered by students in Colleges of Education. It adopted simple random and stratified sampling techniques were used to sample the respondents. In the colleges of education namely Federal College of Education Yola and Adamawa State College of Education Hong stratified sampling was used to sampled 78 students and they were randomly sampled which served as a sample size. The data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency and percentage. In the category of food and nutrition the respondents revealed that restaurant management (81%), bakery- bread making (71%), snacks (83%), cake making and decoration (86%), fast food business (83%), ice cream and yogurt business (87%), preparation of soya milk and other fruit drinks (85%) and jam making (49%). Whereas, in the category of clothing and textiles they disclosed that fashion and designing (88%), dyeing and batik making (73). In the category of Home management, laundry and dry cleaning (72%), housekeeping (74%), soap and body cream production (72%), rug cleaning services (69%) and child development (62%)., which clearly unveiled that learners do acquired numerous skills Home Economics though, they have limited learning in jam making, embroidery, baby-sitting and children's clothing merchandising The study concluded that skills acquired in Home Economics by learners enable them to contribute to economic development of the nation. It was recommended that with the role of Home Economics, there is need to have internship /houseman ship after graduation in Home Economics courses through National Directorate of Employment (NDE) and also, both governmental and non-governmental organizations to provide support to the institution through provision of facilities and equipment that are required in teaching and learning Home Economics.

Keywords: Surveyed, Skills acquisition, Home Economics, Nigerian, Economic. Adamawa

1.0 Introduction

Home Economics, is a discipline that offers great opportunities for self-reliance and job opportunities. At this era of mass retrenchment of workers, unemployment and global economic melt-down, graduates should look inward and create jobs for their livelihood. As government cannot provide job for all, it is pertinent that graduate should be encouraged to be self-employed and assisted with soft loans to start their business and also employ others to reduce the number of unemployment which usually lead to social vices. National development encompasses social and political development as well as economic development which is defined as the attainment of a number of ideas, modernization such as a rise in productivity, social and economic equality, improved institutions and values. Economic development is thus an important part of general development in any society. The main aim of economic development is to raise the standard of living and the general wellbeing of the people in an economy where almost everybody can be self-reliant (Oladokun, 2020). Nigeria as a country cannot operate in isolation, hence in fostering their economic growth and development, perpetrate their national interests and develop their political structures, at the same time protect their territorial integrity and security concerns; they often enter into diplomatic relations with one another (Omodele, 2023). This results to hardship to its citizens as the country cannot supply all that its required without been productive enough to compete with other nations and the price of food items and other goods rises. There is need for Home Economics as a course to promote economy growth through skills acquired by the learners.

The pursuit of entrepreneurial endeavors has emerged as a key driver of innovation, economic growth, and job creation in the dynamic world of global economies. Because the corporate world is ever-changing, people need to be able to handle a variety of situations and grasp possibilities as they present themselves. As a result, developing entrepreneurial skills has become essential to promoting an innovative and enterprise-creating culture. Due to its importance in the socioeconomic advancement of society, the phenomenon of skill acquisition has become particularly significant. When it comes to the economy, acquiring new skills helps to revitalize markets and open up new employment chances for graduates and young people who are out of work. The establishment of graduates and their ability to be employers of labour and entrepreneurs is the primary goal of Home Economics Education. Home Economics as a vocational education is designed to develop skills, abilities, understanding, attitudes, work habits and appreciation, encompassing knowledge and information needed by workers to enter

and make progress in employment. This means that vocational education is skill oriented. Most times when nations are faced with problem of unemployment, the first step towards providing solution is to introduce vocational education into the national education system. Vocational subjects happen to provide skills and competences that will make its recipients employable in industries, self-employed and employers of labour and various areas in Home economics provide the needed skills (Iyam and Bessong, 2019).

The various areas in Home economics include Food and Nutrition, clothing and Textiles, family living and child care, home management, Home Economics education among other and the programmes is to help families realise their needs in order to improve their quality of life. Home economics programmes are based on the needs, problems and interests of people as well as on their available resources. Problems Home economists have to address in developing countries usually stem from lack of food, shelter and clothing. In this regard, there are a number of challenges facing sewing skills acquisition which has impacted negatively on national economic development in Nigeria. The specialty is regarded as inferior to other specialties hence acute shortage of devoted and skilled teachers. Also, lack of adequate training facilities as he stressed that about 50% of the institutions running vocational and technical education in Nigeria are yet to meet approved national standards. In many of the schools, basic facilities such as furniture, laboratories, running water, electricity, machines, computers, etc. are missing (Ozoemena, 2013., Oguntuyi, 2013).

The problems of malnutrition are caused not only by a lack of knowledge but also connect to socio-cultural habits of families, food production, distribution and use. The Homemaker has to know what the nutritional needs of the different family members and must be able to prepare attractive, nutritional meals by using safe and sanitary methods within a limited budget. Housing is more than shelter. It is the space where individuals and families develop physically, psychologically and socially. Good arrangement of space is necessary for activities such as work, rest and recreation and efficient equipment should be used to save time and energy. Adequate privacy for family members as well as sanitation in the house and its environment are important aspects. Clothing not only satisfies physical needs but also acts as an outward sign of a person's role and status in the family and the community. Functional and comfortable clothes are important for individual well-being, but proper construction techniques and care practices will pre- long the usefulness of textile items and maintain hygiene. - As families in developing communities move from a subsistence to a money economy they will

need to become better informed consumers in order to use their resources in the best possible way to satisfy their food, housing and clothing needs. Homemakers need guidance in creating a secure and happy Home atmosphere and therefore need information on child care and development as well as on handling conflict situations to ensure family stability (Erika, 1985). The study therefore, the study surveyed skills acquisition in Home economics as a way forward to promote Nigerian economic. A case study of Colleges of Education in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

The study sought to:-

- i. Identify the various areas of Home economics and the available skills open for students at colleges of education in Adamawa state.
- ii. Examine the impact of the skill acquired on the societal development that is economy development.
- iii. Identify the constraints associated with teaching and learning Home economics in Colleges of Education in Adamawa State.

2. Methodology

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in Colleges of Education in Adamawa state, Nigeria. The state is located in the North-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria, lying between latitude 7° and 11° north and longitude 11° and 14° East of the Greenwich meridian (Adebayo and Tukur, 1999). The state is bordered with Borno to the northwest, Gombe to the west, and Taraba to the southwest, while its eastern border forms part of the national border with Cameroon across the Atlantica Mountains. It takes its name from the historic emirate of Adamawa, with the emirate's old capital of Yola, serving as the capital city of Adamawa state. The state is one of the most heterogeneous in Nigeria, with over 100 indigenous ethnic groups. It was formed in 1991, when the former Gongola state was divided into Adamawa and Taraba states. located in northeastern part of Nigeria (Michael, 2019).

Adamawa is one among the largest State in Nigeria with a landmark of 38.741 km. The State has an estimated projected population of 4,902,100 million people (City Population, 2024). It has annual rainfall ranging from 700mm to 1600mm in the extreme southern part of the state with mean monthly temperature ranging from 26.7C to 27.8 C. The State has a tropical wet and dry climate highly characterized with changing climate and desert encroachment from

the northern part of the state sharing boundary with Borno State. The dry season last from minimum of 5 months November to March, while the wet season lasts from April to October. It had to Colleges of Education namely Federal College of Education Yola and Adamawa State College of Education Hong. The State is naturally divided into two ecological zones: the Guinea Savana and Sudan Savana zones. In general the distribution of vegetation is as a result of rainfall, topography and to a laser extent that of soils. Agriculture is the main stay of about 80% of the inhabitants in the State. Ecological condition of the State permits cultivation of root crops, cereals, legumes and livestock in large numbers. Topographically, it is a mountainous land cross by the large river valleys of Benue, Gongola and Yedzaram. The valleys of the Cameroon, Mandara and Adamawa mountains form part of the landscape.

2.2 Sample and Sampling Technique

Simple stratified random sampling was used to select 78 students from Federal College of Education Yola and Adamawa State College of Education as respondents for the study

2.3 Method of data Analysis

The data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency and percentage.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Skills training in Home Economics in Colleges of Education in Adamawa State

In Table 1, it disclosed the areas of skill training learning by the students of Home Economics in Colleges of Education in Adamawa State which were categories into food and nutrition, clothing and textiles, Home management, nursery management and decoration. In the category of food and nutrition the respondents revealed that restaurant management (81%), bakery- bread making (71%), snacks (83%), cake making and decoration (86%), fast food business (83%), ice cream and yogurt business (87%), preparation of soya milk and other fruit drinks (85%) and jam making (49%). Whereas, in the category of clothing and textiles they disclosed that fashion and designing (88%), dyeing and batik making (73%), embroidery (38%), crocheting and knitting (42%), weaving (40%), fabric and clothing accessories merchandising (83%) and fashion school operation (58%). In the category of Home management, laundry and dry cleaning (72%), housekeeping (74%), soap and body cream production (72%), rug cleaning services (69%) and child development (62%). Likewise, in the category of nursery management it was revealed that daycare centres (86%), baby-sitting (40%)

and children's clothing merchandising (24%). also, in the category of decoration they revealed that event planning and decorations (86%), interior decoration (82%) and making of crafts (56%). This clearly unveiled that learners do acquired numerous skills Home Economics though, they have limited learning in jam making, embroidery, baby-sitting and children's clothing merchandising. With these skill it is apparent that graduates of Home economics can impact positively on the growth of Nigerian economy. This is in line with the findings of Abdulazee., Aminu., Kamoru & Ibraheem (2024) who found that skills exact great impact to economic growth of the nation.

Table 1: Skill training Learn by the students of Home Economics in Colleges of education in Adamawa State (n =78)

Items	Skills	*Frequency	Percentage
Food and Nutrition	Restaurant Management	63	81
	Bakery- Bread making	55	71
	Snacks	65	83
	Cake making and decoration	67	86
	Fast Food business	65	83
	Ice cream and yogurt business	68	87
	Preparation of soya milk and other fruit drinks	51	65
	Jam making	35	49
	Clothing and Textiles	Fashion and Designing	69
Dyeing and batik making		57	73
Embroidery		30	38
Crocheting and knitting		33	42
Weaving		31	40
Fabric and clothing accessories merchandising		65	83
Fashion school operation		45	58
Home Management	Laundry and dry cleaning	56	72
	Housekeeping	58	74
	Soap and body cream production	56	72
	Rug cleaning services	54	69
	Child Development	49	62
Nursery management	Daycare centres	67	86
	Baby sitting	31	40
	Children's clothing merchandising	19	24
Decoration	Event planning and decorations	67	86
	Interior Decoration	64	82
	Making of crafts	44	56

Source: Field survey, 2024

3.2 Impact of the acquired skills by the students of Home Economics in Colleges of Education in Adamawa State on societal development

Table 2 shows the impact of the acquiring skills on the societal development by the students of Home Economics in Colleges of education in Adamawa State where 3 points Likert scale was used with the aid of mean to analyzed the data obtained. It was shown that create employment opportunities (mean score = 2.53), generation of income (mean score =2.47), bring about entrepreneurship (mean score = 2.26), lead to creation of other finished products (mean score = 2.52) and add values to products (mean score = 2.61). This implies that the acquired skills exact great impact on the societal development as it create employment opportunities, generation of income, bring about entrepreneurship, lead to creation of other finished products and add values to products.

Table 2: Impact of the acquiring the skills on the societal development

Statements	Very High	High	Low	Mean Score	Decision
Create employment opportunities	45	30	03	2.53	Agreed
Generation of income	50	21	07	2.47	Agreed
Bring about entrepreneurship	38	22	18	2.26	Agreed
Lead to creation of other finished products	49	21	08	2.52	Agreed
Add values to products	56	04	28	2.61	Agreed

Source: Field survey, 2024

3.3 Constraints associated with teaching and learning Home economics in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State

Table 3 shows the constraints associated with the teaching and learning of Home Economics in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State. The results show that the Home Economics faced major constraints such as materials for learning (65%), skilled personals (87%), poor remunerative to staff concern (86%), corruption practices among staff (83%), institution's academic calendar (83%) and poor funding (71%). This collaborates with the study of Iyam and Bessong (2019) who in their finding revealed that inadequate instructional

materials and man power in the system that can affect effective implementation of the curricula of Home Economics.

Table 3.3: Constraints Associated with the Teaching and Learning of Home Economics in Colleges of Education in Adamawa State

S/N	Items	*Frequency	Percentage
1.	Poor funding	55	71
2.	Corruption practices among staff	65	83
3.	Poor remunerative to staff concern	67	86
4.	Institution's academic calendar	65	83
5.	Skilled personnel	68	87
6.	Materials for Learning	51	65

Source: Field Survey, 2024 *Multiple Responses

4.1 Conclusion

The study unveiled that skills acquired in Home Economics by learners enable them to contribute to economic development of the nation as it was found that learners do acquired numerous skills Home Economics though, they have limited learning in jam making, embroidery, baby-sitting and children's clothing merchandising. the acquired skills exact great impact on the societal development as it creates employment opportunities, generation of income, bring about entrepreneurship, lead to creation of other finished products and add values to products. Also, teaching and learning of Home Economics in the Institution faced major constraints such as materials for learning, skilled personals, poor remunerative to staff concern, corruption practices among staff, institution's academic calendar and poor funding which dwindle it contributions.

4.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings, I recommend the following:-

- i. With the role of Home Economics, there is need to have internship /houseman ship after graduation in Home Economics courses through National Directorate of Employment (NDE)..
- ii. There is need for both governmental and non-governmental organizations to provide support to the institution through provision of facilities and equipment that are required in teaching and learning Home Economics.
- iii. In terms of inadequate funding, both governmental and non-governmental

- organizations should provide enough funds to enhance teaching and learning of Home Economics in the institutions and for the graduates also to kick start their business and invest the knowledge acquired.
- iv. Each laboratory attendants attached to the various areas of Home Economics should be graduates of Home Economics with minimum qualification of NCE so as to assist the lecturer adequately during practical.

References

- Abdulazeez, A. S., Aminu, N. B., Kamoru, L. A. & Ibraheem, S. A. (2024). Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition and Employment Generation in Kwara State , *International Journal Of Advanced Research* 4 (1), 145-155
- Adebayo, A. A. and Tukur, A. L. (1999). Adamawa State in Maps, Publication Department of Geography, Federal University of Technology Yola in COOPERATE with Paraclete Publications. A Division of Paraclete and Sons Nigeria.
- City Population (2024). Population Statistics for Cities. Retrieved June 25, 2024 from www.citypopulation.de
- Erika, K. (1985). Home economics and development, *Development Southern Africa*, 2:1, 89-96,
- Iyam, M. A. and Bessong, M. O. (2019). Home Economics Sewing Skills Acquisition and Sustainable Economic Development in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State, Nigeria. *IJARIE*, 5 (5): 209-217
- Jacob, S., & Ariya, A. (2015). Teaching entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions and the disposition of social studies students towards self-reliance in Plateau State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 3(10), 95-108.
- Michael, A. (2019). "Adamawa State: History, Population, Size, LGAs, Map & More" . NaijaHomeBased . Retrieved October 1, 2024 from www.researchgate.net/publication
- Oguntuyi, A. N (2013). A viable vocational technical education curriculum: A tool for economic and technology development in Nigeria. *Scholarly Journal of Education*, 2(2), 22-26.

- Oladokun, A. (2020). Vocational Home Economics Education: A Veritable Tool for Self Reliance, Poverty Eradication and Sustainable National Development, UJAH, 21(3):213-224
- Onuma, N. (2016). Entrepreneurship education in Nigerian tertiary institutions: A remedy to graduates unemployment. *British journal of education*, 4(5), 16-28.
- Ozoemena S. A. (2013). Vocational and Technical Education: A tool for sustainable development in Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(25), 127-130.
- Padi, A. (2022). Effects of skill acquisition on entrepreneurship development. General systematic review and progress in Ghana , 2147- 4478.